

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B488		
Date:	24 NOV 2009		
Take Off:	13:11:02Z	Z	Z
Landing:	19:25:32Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 14m 30s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: T-NAWDEX

Operating Area: Atlantic – Southwest approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voaden	Directflight
4	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist	Doug Parker	Leeds University
6	Flight manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry/AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Observer	Zoe Clough	BBC
10	Observer	Don Slater	BBC
11	Observer	David Braine	BBC
12	Core Chemistry/AVAPS training	Axel Wellpott	FAAM
13	Mission Scientist 2	John Methven	Reading University
14	Mission Scientist 3	Peter Knippertz	Leeds University
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
Y	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs
Y	Planning charts or plots
Y	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-11-25	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B488
Date: 24 Nov 09

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC still u/s despite vane change. Suspect box/wiring.
2. Turbulence sideslip ports iced 1647, flying in icing in strong crosswind

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Sortie Brief: BAe146 Flight B488 – 24 November 2009

Version 2. Prepared by John Methven, Doug Parker and Ian Renfrew

Mission Scientist 1: John Methven

Mission Scientists: Doug Parker, Peter Knippertz, Tom Frame possibly.

Location: South of Ireland in NOTAM A and the marine sector to its west.

Aims:

- Straight and level runs along and across the cold front, within the marine boundary layer, to measure turbulent fluxes of temperature and humidity.
- Profiling ascent from marine boundary layer through Warm Conveyor Belt (WCB) – a tongue of ascending warm air originating in the central Atlantic. The front is forecast to be rearward sloping, so that the WCB is above and behind (to the northwest side) of the cold front with ~300 km between surface front and tropopause trough.
- High level dropsonde leg across the cold front and WCB.

Item	Time (UTC)	Manoeuvre	Distance (km)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1300	Take off Cranfield, transit towards point A, descending to minimum safe altitude.			
2	1345	Profile descent to minimum safe altitude on arriving at A on warm (near) side of front.		50	50
3	1350	Turn upstream (towards SW) parallel to front for run at MSA (see diagram) to point B.		15	65
4		Turn 90° to cross front heading towards NW at MSA towards point C.		20	85
5	1405	Turn downstream to run at MSA parallel to front towards NE (point D) on cold side.		15	100
6		Turn to cross front at MSA, overshooting point A, to point E.		30	130
7	1510	Turn, heading upstream along front at MSA to point F.		15	145
8		Turn towards NW and cross front at 1500ft to point G		40	185
9	1605	Profile ascent at 1000 ft/min to point H, arriving at maximum altitude. Sunset.		30	215
10	1635	Dropsonde leg at maximum altitude, heading directly across WCB to point I. Releasing 5-7 dropsondes evenly along leg.	~500 km	40	255
11		Return towards base in most fuel efficient manner.	<700 km	50	305
12	1805	Land in Cranfield.			

Notes:

MSA is to be defined as a constant value which can be flown both in and out of rain, with the exception of items 3 and 7, one of which should be at 100ft over the sea.

Sketch of sortie.

A = Warm side of front (~ 51N, 8W).

H = Start of dropsonde leg on northwest side of WCB and front (as far west as we can ~51N, 11W).

I = End of dropsonde leg (~51N, 6W) – leg could be along northern edge of NOTAM A.

B488 10:38:57-18:27:42

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B488

Date:24/11/09

Project:T-NAWDEX

Location:Atlantic/SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
125935		startup	0.59 kft	123	cranfield
131102		T/O	0.58 kft	212	
140933	143940	Profile 1	26.0 - 0.48 kft	241	
143958	145532	Run 1	0.55 - 0.52 kft	237	
145539	145632	Profile 2	0.56 - 1.4 kft	212	
145633	152409	Run 2	1.4 kft	214	
152426	160417	Run 3	1.4 kft	101	
160436	160812	Profile 3	1.4 - 5.0 kft	276	
160819	162906	Run 4	5.0 kft	280	
162930	163513	Profile 4	5.0 - 0.53 kft	304	
163513	170505	Profile 5	0.53 - 29.0 kft	304	
170225		Profile 5	27.1 kft	254	interrupt
170249		Profile 5	27.0 kft	219	resume
170700		Sonde 1	29.1 kft	106	
171405		Sonde 2	29.1 kft	107	
171924		Sonde 3	29.0 kft	105	
172534		Sonde 4	29.1 kft	103	
173108		Sonde 5	29.0 kft	097	
173639		Sonde 6	29.0 kft	090	
174214		Sonde 7	29.0 kft	091	
182532		Land	0.66 kft	209	Cranfield

1300 on Tue 24 Nov

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 24 Nov 2009 1300 UTC

1230 on Tue 24 Nov

13:45 (12:45 UTC)

Sat24.com

Sat24.com EUMETSAT/DWD

1330 on Tue 24 Nov

14:30 (13:30 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

1400 on Tue 24 Nov

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 24 Nov 2009 1400 UTC

1430 on Tue 24 Nov

15:30 (14:30 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

asxx 24/11/2009 12:00 UTC

asxx 24/11/2009 18:00 UTC

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	52323	secs
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	98.92	%
—	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	24.97	m s ⁻¹
—	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	29.16	m s ⁻¹
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	4.37	Kft

All sc

Flight B488 18:27:42

Heading 354 deg Speed 2 knots Height 0.6kft Press 988mb

Lat 52°0.0'N Long 0°36.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 202 deg

Temp 12.14C Dewpoint 10.19C

From 17:40:00 to now

Current values

STATIC PRESSURE
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP
++++ DEW POINT

988.74 mb
12.14 deg C
10.2 deg C

Flight B488 18:03:46

Heading 81 deg Speed 246 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb

Lat 51°48.0'N Long 2°36.0'W Wind 35 ms-1/ 230 deg

Temp -0.97C Dewpoint -20.6C

From 12:28:23 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -2.61 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 51.83 deg (+ve N)

16:30 (15:30 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

17:30 (16:30 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

18:00 (17:00 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	53757	secs
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	95.6	%
—	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	26.97	m s-1
—	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	11.85	m s-1
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.82	Kft

All SC

Flight B488 15:13:38

Heading 45 deg Speed 202 knots Height 1.4kft Press 962mb

Lat 50°0.0'N Long 9°54.0'W Wind 12 ms-1/258 deg

Temp 8.22C Dewpoint 9.95C

From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 54816 secs
— EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP 308.14 K
— POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE 284.43 K

All sc

New plot, same times

Flight B488 15:13:38

Heading 45 deg Speed 202 knots Height 1.4kft Press 962mb

Lat 50°0.0'N Long 9°54.0'W Wind 12 ms-1/258 deg

Temp 8.22C Dewpoint 9.95C

From 13:29:00 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 54816 secs
RELATIVE HUMIDITY 1.00

All sc

Flight B488 15:25:55

Heading 101 deg Speed 208 knots Height 1.4kft Press 962mb

Lat 50°24.0'N Long 8°48.0'W Wind 20 ms-1/277 deg

Temp 8.55C Dewpoint 7.75C

From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

55554 secs

EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP

305.07 K

POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

284.70 K

All sc

New plot, same times

Flight B488 15:25:55

Heading 101 deg Speed 208 knots Height 1.4kft Press 962mb

Lat 50°24.0'N Long 8°48.0'W Wind 20 ms-1/277 deg

Temp 8.55C Dewpoint 7.75C

From 13:29:00 to now

Flight B488 15:38:38
 Heading 113 deg Speed 220 knots Height 1.4kft Press 962mb
 Lat 50°18.0'N Long 7°36.0'W Wind 28 ms-1/ 207 deg
 Temp 11.56C Dewpoint 10.04C
 From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	56316	secs
—	EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP	311.66	K
—	POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE	287.82	K

All SC

New plot, same times

Flight B488 15:38:38
 Heading 113 deg Speed 220 knots Height 1.4kft Press 962mb
 Lat 50°18.0'N Long 7°36.0'W Wind 28 ms-1/ 207 deg
 Temp 11.56C Dewpoint 10.04C
 From 13:29:00 to now

Current values

Flight B488 15:46:37

Heading 212 deg Speed 223 knots Height 1.3kft Press 963mb

Lat 50°5.0'N Long 7°12.0'W Wind 31 ms-1/ 207 deg

Temp 11.35C Dewpoint 9.96C

From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

56796 secs

EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP

311.28 K

POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

287.59 K

All SC

New plot, same times

Flight B488 15:46:36

Heading 212 deg Speed 223 knots Height 1.3kft Press 963mb

Lat 50°5.0'N Long 7°12.0'W Wind 31 ms-1/ 207 deg

Temp 11.35C Dewpoint 9.96C

From 13:29:00 to now

Flight B488 16:04:47
 Heading 276 deg Speed 215 knots Height 1.5kft Press 958mb
 Lat 49°30.0'N Long 8°0.0'W Wind 32 ms-1/ 209 deg
 Temp 11.32C Dewpoint 10.29C
 From 12:51:47 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 57885 secs
 EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP 312.33 K
 POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE 287.94 K

All SC

New plot, same times

Flight B488 16:04:46
 Heading 276 deg Speed 215 knots Height 1.5kft Press 958mb
 Lat 49°30.0'N Long 8°0.0'W Wind 32 ms-1/ 209 deg
 Temp 11.32C Dewpoint 10.29C
 From 13:29:00 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 57885 secs
 All SC

Speed 215 knots Height 1.5kft Press 958mb
 Lat 49°30.0'N Long 8°0.0'W Wind 32 ms-1/ 209 deg
 Dewpoint 10.29C
 From 13:29:00 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 57885 secs
 All SC

-8.07
 49.58

Flight B488 16:29:38
 Heading 303 deg Speed 227 knots Height 4.9kft Press 843mb
 Lat 50°0.0'N Long 10°0.0'W Wind 19 ms-1/ 256 deg
 Temp 0.96C Dewpoint 2.06C
 From 12:51:47 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 59376 secs
 — EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP 303.79 K
 — POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE 287.77 K

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 59376 secs
 — RELATIVE HUMIDITY 100 %
 — NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT 4.81 m s-1
 — EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT 19.36 m s-1
 — PRESSURE HEIGHT 4.98 Kft

Flight B488 16:29:38
 Heading 303 deg Speed 227 knots Height 4.9kft Press 843mb
 Lat 50°0.0'N Long 10°0.0'W Wind 19 ms-1/ 256 deg
 Temp 0.96C Dewpoint 2.06C
 From 12:28:23 to now

Current values
 — GIN LONGITUDE -10.05 deg (+ve)
 — GIN LATITUDE 50.03 deg (+ve)

Flight 8488 14:41:50
 Heading 214 deg Speed 215 knots Height 0.5kft Press 993mb
 Lat 50°18.0'N Long 8°0.0'W Wind 25 ms-1/ 201 deg
 Temp 13.55C Dewpoint 10.78C
 From 12:51:47 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 52908 secs
 — EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP 311.3 K
 — POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE 287.24 K

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 52908 secs
 — RELATIVE HUMIDITY 95.82 %
 — NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT 23.66 m s-1
 — EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT 9.23 m s-1
 — PRESSURE HEIGHT 0.54 Kft

Flight B488 16:39:06

Heading 287 deg Speed 219 knots Height 4.6kft Press 853mb

Lat 50°18.0'N Long 10°42.0'W Wind 18 ms-1/ 242 deg

Temp 0.23C Dewpoint 0.83C

From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	59946	secs
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	100	%
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	42.02	ppb
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	4.67	kft
—	CO MIXING RATIO	110.65	pbb

All sc
● ○ ○ ○ ○ ○

Flight B488 14:56:01

Heading 211 deg Speed 215 knots Height 0.8kft Press 982mb

Lat 49°42.0'N Long 8°36.0'W Wind 30 ms-1/ 197 deg

Temp 13.33C Dewpoint 10.55C

From start to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ RELATIVE HUMIDITY
++++ OZONE MIXING RATIO
++++ CO MIXING RATIO

0.86 Kft
95.81 %
40.02 ppb
104.17 pbb

All
●○○○

Flight B488 13:46:13

Heading 251 deg Speed 318 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 51°42.0'N Long 3°18.0'W Wind 46 ms-1/ 247 deg

Temp -32.35C Dewpoint -40.4C

From start to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ RELATIVE HUMIDITY
++++ OZONE MIXING RATIO
++++ CO MIXING RATIO

26.04 Kft
86.06 %
37.55 ppb
91.29 pbb

All
●
○

Flight B488 18:10:28

Heading 64 deg Speed 249 knots Height 10.0kft Press 695mb

Lat 51°54.0'N Long 1°42.0'W Wind 37 ms-1/ 229 deg

Temp -0.91C Dewpoint -25.83C

From 16:35:00 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT
OZONE MIXING RATIO

65427

39.93

secs

ppb

All sc

Flight B488 18:27:42

Heading 354 deg Speed 2 knots Height 0.6kft Press 988mb

Lat 52°0.0'N Long 0°36.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 202 deg

Temp 12.14C Dewpoint 10.19C

From 16:35:00 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT
OZONE MIXING RATIO

66462
31.09

secs
ppb

All sc

Flight B488 17:49:19
 Heading 75 deg Speed 333 knots Height 22.0kft Press 426mb
 Lat 51°18.0'N Long 4°42.0'W Wind 21 ms-1/2 deg
 Temp -24.15C Dewpoint -42.57C
 From 16:35:00 to now

Lat 51°18.0'N Long 4°42.0'W Wind 21 ms-1/2 deg
 Temp -24.15C Dewpoint -42.57C
 From 13:29:00 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 64158 secs All SC

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	64158	secs	<input type="checkbox"/> All <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SC
RELATIVE HUMIDITY	71.21	%	
NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	-21.67	m s ⁻¹	
EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	-0.86	m s ⁻¹	

Pre-Flighter's Log

NOV

Flight No: B 488

Pre-Flighter: JT

<input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Location	Action	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	Instrument checked and noisy
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	CO flow good - before today
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	garage for 2000
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	IS THIS STILL RED WIRE??
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	RECEIVED MESSAGE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	NOT FITTED
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3876 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	<input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Location	Action	Comments
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3786 CPC	Drained	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
<u>External Checks</u>				
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butano!**
47	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
48	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
49	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
50	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
51	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
52	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
53	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

D20091124_174216.3 091959097 T-NAWDEX, B488 none, none

Flight B488 16:42:45

Heading 285 deg Speed 231 knots Height 8.1kft Press 748mb

Lat 50°24.0'N Long 10°54.0'W Wind 25 ms-1/ 243 deg

Temp -7.89C Dewpoint -6.37C

From 16:35:00 to now

Current values

++++	STATIC PRESSURE	748.95	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-7.9	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-6.38	deg C
++++	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	11.34	m s-1
++++	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	22.45	m s-1

Flight B488 14:54:54

Heading 212 deg Speed 212 knots Height 0.5kft Press 994mb

Lat 49°48.0'N Long 8°36.0'W Wind 24 ms-1/ 201 deg

Temp 14.0C Dewpoint 10.92C

From start to now

Current values

STATIC PRESSURE
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP
++++ DEW POINT

994.27 mb
14 deg C
10.93 deg C

Flight B488 17:07:26

Heading 106 deg Speed 363 knots Height 29.0kft Press 314mb

Lat 50°48.0'N Long 12°6.0'W Wind 81 ms-1/ 202 deg

Temp -42.53C Dewpoint -41.23C

From 16:35:00 to now

Current values

####	STATIC PRESSURE	314.26	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-42.53	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-41.23	deg C
++++	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	74.67	m s-1
++++	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	31.49	m s-1

Flight B488 13:47:57

Heading 251 deg Speed 330 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 51°36.0'N Long 3°30.0'W Wind 47 ms-1/ 247 deg

Temp -32.25C Dewpoint -39.8C

From start to now

Current values

STATIC PRESSURE

359.04

mb

DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP

-32.26

deg C

DEW POINT

-39.81

deg C

Flight B488 16:41:37

Heading 287 deg Speed 230 knots Height 7.0kft Press 780mb

Lat 50°18.0'N Long 10°48.0'W Wind 22 ms-1/ 242 deg

Temp -5.63C Dewpoint -3.91C

From 15:08:05 to now

Current values

++++ STATIC PRESSURE
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP
++++ DEW POINT

780.13 mb
-5.64 deg C
-3.92 deg C

Flight B488 13:43:07

Heading 253 deg Speed 344 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 51°42.0'N Long 3°0.0'W Wind 43 ms-1/ 252 deg

Temp -31.31C Dewpoint -37.99C

From 12:57:38 to now

Current values

STATIC PRESSURE

359.21

mb

++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP

-31.32

deg C

++++ DEW POINT

-38

deg C

Flight B488 14:31:03

Heading 238 deg Speed 230 knots Height 5.1kft Press 838mb

Lat 50°30.0'N Long 7°18.0'W Wind 40 ms-1/ 233 deg

Temp 4.22C Dewpoint 4.29C

From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	52263	secs
—	EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP	310.66	K
—	POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE	291.66	K

All SC

Flight B488 13:24:05

Heading 243 deg Speed 308 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb

Lat 52°12.0'N Long 1°0.0'W Wind 36 ms-1/ 248 deg

Temp -0.19C Dewpoint -19.46C

From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

48243 secs

EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP

306.39 K

POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

302.68 K

All sc

Flight B488 13:53:50

Heading 250 deg Speed 343 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 51°30.0'N Long 4°6.0'W Wind 49 ms-1/ 243 deg

Temp -32.64C Dewpoint -55.6C

From 12:51:47 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

50028 secs

All sc

— EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP

322.39 K

— POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

322.17 K

1500 on Tue 24 Nov

1530 on Tue 24 Nov

1600 on Tue 24 Nov

1630 on Tue 24 Nov

1700 on Tue 24 Nov

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
Tuesday 1400Z 24/11/2009 (t+11h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
Tuesday 1400Z 24/11/2009 (t+11h)

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
 Tuesday 1500Z 24/11/2009 (t+12h)

-45 -40 -35 -30 -25 -20 -15 -10 -5 0 5 10 15 20 25 30 35 40 45

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
 Tuesday 1500Z 24/11/2009 (t+12h)

0.1 - 0.25 0.25 - 0.5 0.5 - 1 1 - 2
 2 - 4 4 - 8 8 - 16 16 - 32
 32+ mm/hr

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
 Tuesday 1600Z 24/11/2009 (t+13h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
 Tuesday 1600Z 24/11/2009 (t+13h)

0.1 - 0.25 0.25 - 0.5 0.5 - 1 1 - 2
 2 - 4 4 - 8 8 - 16 16 - 32
 32+ mm/hr

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
 Tuesday 1700Z 24/11/2009 (t+14h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
 Tuesday 1700Z 24/11/2009 (t+14h)

0.1 - 0.25 0.25 - 0.5 0.5 - 1 1 - 2
 2 - 4 4 - 8 8 - 16 16 - 32
 32+ mm/hr

1000 on Tue 24 Nov

11:00 (10:00 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
 Tuesday 1400Z 24/11/2009 (t+11h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
 Tuesday 1400Z 24/11/2009 (t+11h)

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
Tuesday 1500Z 24/11/2009 (t+12h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
Tuesday 1500Z 24/11/2009 (t+12h)

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
 Tuesday 1600Z 24/11/2009 (t+13h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
 Tuesday 1600Z 24/11/2009 (t+13h)

0.1 - 0.25 0.25 - 0.5 0.5 - 1 1 - 2
 2 - 4 4 - 8 8 - 16 16 - 32
 32+ mm/hr

UKV op Temperature at 1.5m [C]
 Tuesday 1700Z 24/11/2009 (t+14h)

UKV op Precipitation rate [mm/hr] and PMSL
 Tuesday 1700Z 24/11/2009 (t+14h)

0.1 - 0.25 0.25 - 0.5 0.5 - 1 1 - 2
 2 - 4 4 - 8 8 - 16 16 - 32
 32+ mm/hr

1000 on Tue 24 Nov

11:00 (10:00 UTC)

Sat24.com

Source: EUMETSAT/DWD

EVVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 24 Nov 2009 1500 UTC

EVVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 24 Nov 2009 1600 UTC

Flight B488 16:38:05

Heading 290 deg Speed 221 knots Height 3.6kft Press 885mb

Lat 50°18.0'N Long 10°36.0'W Wind 17 ms-1/ 242 deg

Temp 2.53C Dewpoint 3.22C

From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	59883	secs
—	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	8.07	m s-1
—	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	15.73	m s-1
—	VERTICAL WIND COMPONENT	0.37	m s-1
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	3.68	Kft

All sc
○○○○○

Temp 8.31C Dewpoint 9.93C

From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	54762	secs
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	100	%
—	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	6.11	m s-1
—	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	16.38	m s-1
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	1.39	Kft

All sc

Temp 11.68C Dewpoint 10.52C

From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	56082	secs
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	98.22	%
—	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	24.21	m s ⁻¹
—	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	13.28	m s ⁻¹
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	1.37	Kft

All sc
○○○○○

Flight B488 14:42:39

Heading 216 deg Speed 212 knots Height 0.5kft Press 994mb

Lat 50°18.0'N Long 8°0.0'W Wind 22 ms-1/ 205 deg

Temp 13.54C Dewpoint 10.99C

From start to now

Current values

++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.51	Kft
●●●●	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	96.14	%
++++	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	20.39	m s-1
++++	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	9.64	m s-1

All

Flight B488 13:47:21

Heading 252 deg Speed 327 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 51°36.0'N Long 3°24.0'W Wind 46 ms-1/ 248 deg

Temp -32.26C Dewpoint -44.04C

From start to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
+ + + + RELATIVE HUMIDITY
+ + + + NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT
+ + + + EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT

26.05 Kft
80.14 %
17.17 m s-1
43.58 m s-1

All
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WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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Radar

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Data Accept
 Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
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Gain: Max
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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Data Accept

Filter 1

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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Data Accept
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WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
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WEATHER

Range: 80
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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Filter 1

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WEATHER

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Gain: Max
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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
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Radar

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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[Back] [Fwd] 25

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Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

Radar

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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[Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept

Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

20 40 60 80

Radar

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25

Data Accept

 Filter

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WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

Radar

Search
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Data Accept
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WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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Radar

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Data Accept
 Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Filter 1

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Range: 80
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Radar

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step

[Back] [Fwd] 25

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Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
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WX

Radar

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Define

Step
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Data Accept
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Gain: Max
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Radar

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Define [Back] [Fwd]

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[Back] [Fwd] 25

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Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
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